

Effect of Lateral Substituent on Mesomorphism

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Two mesogenic homologous series, (I) 4(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-ethylanilines and (II) 4(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-phenetidines with a bulky methoxy lateral substituent are synthesized. The effect of lateral methoxy group on mesomorphic properties is evaluated. The mesomorphic-isotropic transition temperatures are drastically reduced, but the effect on solid-mesomorphic transition temperatures is negligible.

THE synthesis of new low melting liquid crystals has acquired importance as ambient liquid crystals are finding wide technological applications. Lateral substituents are known to depress the melting points very effectively^{1,2}. As methyl and chloro groups with small size decrease the melting points, it was thought that bulky methoxy group with much bigger size might lower the melting points to almost room temperature and hence two homologous series (I and II) comprising thirteen members each have been synthesised and their mesogenic behaviour has been studied.

Experimental

- (i) 4-*n*-Alkoxybenzoic acids and 4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chlorides were prepared by the method of Dave and Vora³.
- (ii) 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzaldehydes were prepared as described elsewhere⁴.
- (iii) 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-ethylanilines were prepared by condensing 4(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzaldehydes (0.01 mole) with equimolar quantities of *p*-ethylaniline in ethanol and refluxing for about 3 to 4 hr. Schiff bases separated on cooling, were crystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture until constant melting points were obtained. These are summarised in Table 1. The elemental analytical data were satisfactory.
- (iv) 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-phenetidines were prepared as above, by taking *p*-phenetidine in place of *p*-ethylaniline. The transition temperatures are summarised in Table 1. The elemental analytical data were satisfactory.
- (v) The melting points and the transition temperatures were determined by using a Mettler FP-2 polarizing microscope equipped with a heating stage. The accuracy of transition temperatures is within $\pm 0.5^\circ$.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R'	Transition temp. °C		
			Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
Series I					
1.	Methyl	Ethyl	—	(140.0)*	160.0
2.	Ethyl	Ethyl	—	(167.0)	170.0
3.	Propyl	Ethyl	—	(186.5)	139.5
4.	Butyl	Ethyl	—	122.0	150.0
5.	Pentyl	Ethyl	—	113.5	127.0
6.	Hexyl	Ethyl	—	108.0	129.0
7.	Heptyl	Ethyl	—	(128.0)	188.0
8.	Octyl	Ethyl	—	(119.0)	127.0
9.	Decyl	Ethyl	—	(110.0)	111.0
10.	Dodecyl	Ethyl	—	(105.0)	107.0
11.	Tetradecyl	Ethyl	—	(103.0)	111.0
12.	Hexadecyl	Ethyl	—	(93.0)	104.0
13.	Octadecyl	Ethyl	(79.0)	(93.5)	100.0
* Values in parantheses indicate monotropic.					
Series II					
14.	Methyl	Ethoxy	—	188.0	209.0
15.	Ethyl	Ethoxy	—	153.0	224.0
16.	Propyl	Ethoxy	—	138.0	200.0
17.	Butyl	Ethoxy	—	142.0	198.0
18.	Pentyl	Ethoxy	—	134.0	180.5
19.	Hexyl	Ethoxy	—	129.5	175.0
20.	Heptyl	Ethoxy	—	110.5	165.0
21.	Octyl	Ethoxy	—	121.0	169.0
22.	Decyl	Ethoxy	—	103.0	148.0
23.	Dodecyl	Ethoxy	—	100.0	140.0
24.	Tetradecyl	Ethoxy	—	104.0	185.5
25.	Hexadecyl	Ethoxy	—	104.0	128.0
26.	Octadecyl	Ethoxy	—	98.0	120.0

Discussion

Series I. 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-ethylanilines: Thirteen members of the series were synthesised. The earlier members, i.e., methoxy to propoxy derivatives exhibit monotropic nematic mesophase, the middle members, i.e., butoxy to hexyloxy derivatives are enantiotropic nematic while heptyloxy to octadecyloxy derivatives are monotropic nematic. The octadecyloxy derivative also exhibits monotropic smectic mesophase

along with nematic mesophase, whereas in the case of the corresponding unsubstituted series 4(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy) benzylidene-4''-ethylanilines, [series (A)], the smectic mesophases commence from hexyloxy derivative as monotropic phase⁵. In our earlier work⁴ where the end ethyl group is replaced by methyl group (series III) no smectic mesophase is observed.

The nematic-isotropic transition temperature curve falls as series is ascended and exhibits usual odd-even effect (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-ethylanilines.
 Solid-mesomorphic or isotropic liquid and
 ○—○ Nematic-isotropic liquid.

Series II. 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-phenetidines: Thirteen Schiff bases were synthesised. All of them exhibit enantiotropic nematic mesophase. No smectic phase is observed even in the last member of the series, whereas in the case of the corresponding unsubstituted homologous series 4(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy) benzylidene-4''-phenetidines, [series (B)], the smectic mesophase is observed with decyloxy derivative⁶. In our earlier work⁴ where the end ethoxy group is replaced by methoxy group (series IV), no smectic mesophase is observed.

The nematic-isotropic transition temperature curve exhibits odd-even effect upto pentyloxy derivative (Fig. 2).

Reference to Table 2 suggests that the average nematic-isotropic thermal stability of present two homologous series I and II is much depressed compared to the corresponding unsubstituted homologous series A and B, respectively. The molecular geometry of these series is given in Fig. 3.

TABLE 2—AVERAGE THERMAL STABILITIES

	Series			
	I	II	A	B
Nematic-Isotropic (C ₁ - C _{1,6})	123.1	167.8	211.7	247.6

Fig. 2. 4(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxy benzylidene-4''-phenetidines.

Fig. 3. Molecular geometry of different series.

The geometry of these series indicates that the molecular skeleton of series I, II and A, B is essentially the same, except that the series I and II have lateral methoxy substituent. Therefore, the depression in the nematic thermal stabilities may be attributed to the presence of a bulky methoxy group, in series I and II. It is reported that the hydrogen atom *ortho* to an ester linkage or an azomethine linkage imparts acoplanarity to the molecules of the system^{7,8}. In the present series a bulky methoxy group is *ortho* to an ester linkage. Hence one would expect more non-linearity in the molecules of series I and II compared to those of series A and B. The increased acoplanarity of the molecules of series I and II is also confirmed by taking uv spectra of the two systems (Fig. 4).

The increase in acoplanarity decreases the mesomorphic-mesomorphic and mesomorphic-isotropic transition temperatures. This explains the lower

Fig. 4

○—○ Series B
 ×—× Series II

thermal stabilities of series I and II compared to series A and B.

The introduction of a lateral substituent also decreases the solid-mesomorphic transition temperatures^{1,2}. However, in the present work, the solid-mesomorphic transition temperatures are not much

reduced compared to similar unsubstituted homologous series.

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